

ISic3153

Fragment of a Latin inscription recording building works

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 632

Physical Description

A fragment of a marble slab, broken on all sides, and heavily weathered / eroded on the lower left of the front face

Dimensions

Height 20 cm

Width 26 cm

Depth 3 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: 081506

1. [---]
2. [---]erata ul y,i [s c---]
3. [---]o darem et decr[e]ver [unt---]
4. [---u]t inarentur utq (ue) ev [eherentur ---]
5. [---] nec sola haec erogata s [unt ---]
6. [---]E sestertios C̄C̄L m (ilia) n (ummum) summi [nistrata sunt]
7. [---i]mpedirentur ego de m [eo supplevi]
8. [---] trecentoru [m---]
9. [---Aug]usteum opus [defueret]
10. [--- consensum decurionu]m expugn [avi ---]

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Translation (it)

Commentary

One of two fragments (the other is ISic1664), similar in palaeography and material, which may or may not be part of a single text (commonly edited as such), and which may or may not in turn be further fragments of the letter of Iulius Paternus (ISic0308). The fragments were considered by Mommsen and others (e.g. Manganaro 1989) to be part of the letter of Iulius Paternus of CIL 10.7024.i (ISic0308), published by Mommsen as 10.7024.ii and iii. However Manganaro (1959), and more recently Korhonen (2004), consider these two fr. to be part of a separate but contextually similar inscription, recording sums of money and building works linked to the port, and so probably also by Iulius Paternus, or under him. Korhonen correctly observes that it is not necessary that the two fragments CIL 10.7024.ii (this text) and iii (ISic1664) come from a single text; hence they are published separately here. Note that Manganaro 1989 reported the smallest fragment, ISic1664, to be lost (since rediscovered in the Museo Civico).

Digital identifiers:

TM 653658

EDR 081506

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